

Clinical Profile of Patients with Multi-Organ Dysfunction Syndrome in Patients of Sepsis in Rural set up MICU

Samir R Desai, *J D Lakhani

Department of Medicine, GMERS Medical College, Valsad, *SBKS Medical Institute & RC, Pipariya, Vadodara(Gujarat)

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to assess morbidity and mortality in patients with sepsis, severe sepsis and multi-organ dysfunction syndrome (MODS) with respect to different organs. Fifty patients having evidence of sepsis on day of admission were studied. Detailed history, clinical assessment and routine laboratory investigations including blood culture was done. The patients were defined with severe sepsis and MODS as per ACCP/SCCM guidelines of 1992. Tropical sepsis (malaria and puerperal) was an important problem in our rural based MICU. Multi-organ dysfunction syndrome was the leading cause of mortality (48%). The difference in mortality rate between severe sepsis (10%) group and MODS (56.4%) group was statistically significant. In our study, lung (80%) was the most common organ affected followed by kidneys (78%) on day of admission. Metabolic failure was least common, occurring in only 23% patients on day of admission. But hematologic failure was persistent and most common organ failure after 3 days of admission. Patients with lung and metabolic acidosis on the day of admission had unfavourable outcome. However, persistence of any organ dysfunction beyond 3 days carried worse prognosis except hematological involvement. The difference of mortality between MODS and severe sepsis group was statistically significant. Thus, early diagnosis is necessary before MODS sets in.

KEY WORDS: ICU, MODS, sepsis, SIRS.

INTRODUCTION:

Sepsis, also known as the sepsis syndrome or Systemic Inflammatory Response Syndrome (SIRS), is the combination of inflammation throughout the body, problems with the blood's clotting mechanism (coagulopathy), and low blood pressure (hypotension). All three are part of the body's immune response to infection. In its most severe form, sepsis can drastically reduce blood flow to the major organs, leading eventually to septic shock, widespread organ failure and death.^[1]

Sepsis remains the most important cause of MODS all over the world.^[2,3] In India, especially in rural set up, we come across the usual causes of sepsis and MODS encountered in the West in addition to the special infections peculiar to tropical and developing countries. Systemic Inflammatory Response Syndrome

(SIRS) is defined as widespread inflammatory response that occurs following one of many bodily insults, including infection, trauma, pancreatitis or burns. Sepsis is now the tenth leading cause of death among older adults in the United States. Over the last decade, not only has sepsis become more common but it has also become more deadly.^[4,5,6]

Multi-organ dysfunction syndrome is the leading cause of morbidity and mortality in critically ill patients.^[7] MODS has been defined as progressive dysfunction of two or more organ system following an acute threat to systemic homeostasis as per ACCP/SCCM Consensus Committee - 1992.^[8] MODS has been major concern to the intensivists.

In our present study, we tried to evaluate the severity of patients with severe sepsis and MODS and put comparative data between them. It also focused on which organ involvement is increasingly common and which organ involvement should give an alarming sign to the physician.

The aim of this study was to assess (a) Multi-organ dysfunction syndrome in patients having severe

Corresponding Author: **Dr. Samir R Desai (Desai S.)**, Tithal Road, Valsad - 396001 (Gujarat).
Phone No.: +91 09327344499
E-mail: drsamirdesai@gmail.com

sepsis (MODS in sepsis), (b) prevalence of different organ involved in MODS and (c) morbidity and mortality of patients with sepsis, severe sepsis and multi-organ dysfunction syndrome with respect to different organs.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This prospective study was undertaken at Shree Krishna Hospital, Karamsad attached to Pramukh Swami Medical College, Karamsad after the approval from Human Research Ethics Committee. The study was carried out for one and half years and 50 patients were included in the study. The patients with sepsis as defined by the 'American College of Chest Physicians/Society of Critical Care Medicine (ACCP/SCCM) Consensus Committee - 1992' were included in the study. The detailed history, clinical examination and all the relevant laboratory investigations were done including blood culture.

Study Definitions:^[7,8]

In the present study the conditions were defined according to standard practice and based on relevant literature: a) *Sepsis*: SIRS that has a proven or suspected microbial etiology; b) *Severe sepsis*: Sepsis with one or more signs of one organ dysfunction. The definition of severe sepsis included 8 organs; c) *MODS*: If dysfunction of more than one organ occurred as per severe sepsis definition requiring intervention to maintain homeostasis the case was called to have MODS; d) Organ dysfunction was defined^[9] as follows: i) *Cardiovascular*: Arterial systolic blood pressure <90mmHg or mean arterial pressure <70mmHg pressure that responds to intravenous fluids; ii) *Renal*: Urine output < 0.5ml/kg per hour for 1 hour despite adequate fluid resuscitation or S. creatinine >1.2mg/dl; iii) *Respiratory*: PaO₂/FiO₂ < 400 or, if the lung is the only dysfunctional organ, <200; iv) *Hematological*: Platelet counts <1,50,000/ul or 50% decrease in platelet count from highest value recorded in previous 3 days; v) *Unexplained metabolic acidosis*: A pH <7.30 or a base deficit >5.0meq/lit and a plasma lactate level >1.5 times upper limit of normal for reporting lab; vi) *Adequate fluid resuscitation*: Pulmonary artery wedge pressure >12mm/Hg or central venous pressure >8mmHg; vii) *Liver*^[7]: A bilirubin level of >1.2mg/dl; viii) *Neurological*^[7]: A GCS score less than 15.

We categorized the patients based on above definition into sepsis, severe sepsis and multi-organ

dysfunction syndrome. Then we studied their morbidity, mortality and pattern of different organ involvement. We also observed the effect of various aggressive treatment modalities like ventilator, vaso-pressors and dialysis.

Exclusion Criteria:

Following patients were excluded from the study: a) Patients with pre-existing chronic organ dysfunction; b) Patients who left against medical advice.

Statistical analysis:

We had analyzed various profiles between two groups viz. survivor group which included the patients who were successfully discharged after recovery and non-survivor group which included the patients who died. We also found whether there was any statistical difference in any of the above mentioned profiles between survivor group and non-survivor group. SPSS software version 10 was used. Student's paired "t" test was applied to study significance of difference in two groups. Unconditional logistic regression model was used to evaluate association of various factors in survivors and non survivors.

Ethical Issues:

There was no ethical issue involved in it as it was an observational study and we didn't interfered in the treatment of the patients.

RESULTS:

The mortality rate of patients with sepsis in our ICU was 48%. This rate was slightly higher compared to other studies. We had 78% patients of MODS, 20% patients of severe sepsis and rest 2% patients had sepsis without MODS. The mortality rate of patients of MODS was 56.4%. There were total 39 patients who had multi-organ dysfunction syndrome on day of admission and 2 patients developed MODS after admission. So total 41(82%) out of 50 patients developed MODS during their entire stay.

We analyzed the MODS according to different organ involvement, whether the organ was involved on day of admission or later and their effect on ultimate outcome.

In patients who developed MODS on day of admission lung was the most common organ involved. The frequency of involvement of lung was 80% (in 40 patients). The second frequent involvement was of

kidney, which was present in 39(78%) patients. Liver and CNS were involved in equal proportion in 34(68%) patients. Hematological and CVS were involvement was present in 32 and 29 patients respectively. Metabolic acidosis, which was the least common finding as far as MODS are concerned, was present in 23(46%) patients.

Twenty Three out of 40 patient who had lung involvement expired. The difference of lung involvement in survivor group and non-survivor group was statistically significant ($p=0.01$). Similarly, 15 out of 23 patients who had metabolic acidosis expired. The difference here again between survivor group and non-survivor group who had metabolic acidosis was statistically significant ($p=0.02$). The involvement of other organ viz. renal, CVS, hematological, liver and CNS in survivor group and non-survivor group was not significant.

Hematological involvement was the most common MODS feature after admission. It was found in 31 patients. Lung was involved in 25 and renal in 24 patients. CNS and liver were affected in 20 and 17 patient respectively, whereas there was CVS involvement and metabolic acidosis in 15 and 12 patients respectively.

The remarkable observation in the organ involvement after admission was that the difference in survivor and nonsurvivor group for each organ was statistically significant except for hematological involvement. Out of 31 patients who had hematological involvement, 17 expired and 14 survived. The difference was not significant statistically (Table 3).

Ventilator therapy was used in total 38(76%) patients of which 24 were non-survivor (61.5%; $n=38$). The difference in discharge and non-survivor group of use of ventilator therapy was statistically not significant. However, noticeable point is that all non-survivor patients were put on ventilator.

It is evident that patient who had MODS & Severe Sepsis on day of admission had statistically significant difference in their mortality ($p=0.000$); [Table 1].

Table 1: Staging on day 1. (n=50)

Stage	Survivors	Non-survivors	Total (%)
MODS	17 (43.6%)	22 (56.4%)	39 (78%)
Severe sepsis	9 (90%)	1 (10%)	10 (20%)
Sepsis	0	1 (100%)	1 (02%)
Total	26 (52%)	24 (48%)	50 (100%)

Table 2: Different organ involvement on admission: (n = 50)

Organ	Survivors	Non-survivors	Total (%)
Lung	17	23	40 (80%)
Renal	19	20	39 (78%)
CVS	16	13	29 (58%)
Haematological	16	16	32 (64%)
Metabolic acidosis	8	15	23 (46%)
Liver	16	18	34 (68%)
CNS	18	16	34 (68%)

Table 3: Different organ involvement after admission (after 3 days) (n = 50)

Organ	Survivors	Non-survivors	Total
Lung	7	18	25 (50 %)
Renal	9	15	24 (48 %)
CVS	2	13	15 (30 %)
Haematological	14	17	31 (62 %)
Metabolic acidosis	1	11	12 (24 %)
Liver	5	12	17 (34 %)
CNS	0	20	20 (40 %)

Table 4: Treatment modalities and outcome (n = 50)

		Survivors	Non-Survivor	Total (%)
Ventilator	Yes	14	24	38(76%)
	No	12	00	12(24%)
Vasopressor	Yes	16	21	37(74%)
	No	10	03	13(26%)
Dialysis	Yes	04	04	08(16%)
	No	22	20	42(84%)
Surgical intervention	Yes	08	06	14(28%)
	No	18	18	36(72%)

DISCUSSION:

Tropical sepsis (malaria and puerperal) was an important problem in our rural based MICU. The most common cause of sepsis was malaria (24%) followed by Pneumonia (14%), Puerperal sepsis (12%) & Cellulitis (12%). The aetiology of sepsis in remaining patients was Cholecystitis (12%), UTI (10%), Meningitis (8%) and Pancreatitis (8%).

We had total 41 patients of MODS, of which 24 died. Hence the mortality rate of patients who had MODS was 56.4%. We found that overall mortality rate was 48% which was higher compared to other studies. But we had more patient of MODS (78% patient) which might have accounted for higher mortality rate. The mortality rate for sepsis, severe sepsis and MODS was 100%, 10% and 56.4%

respectively. We had only one patient of sepsis, which was of burns (85% burns) which might account for false high mortality rate in sepsis group. Otherwise the difference in mortality rate between severe sepsis (10%) group and MODS (56.4%) group was statistically significant ($p=0.000$). Hence, as the number of organ involved increases, it should give alarming sign to the physician.

There were 40% patients who had diagnosis of SIRS prior to admission, while 60% patients had diagnosis of SIRS on admission. The mortality rate was 60% in patients who had SIRS prior to admission as compared to 40% in patients who had diagnosis of SIRS on admission. This again signifies the importance that patients of sepsis have a better chance of survival if they come to hospital earlier in their course of disease. This could be attributed to the fact that majority of the patients over here came after being treated in the periphery. So the patient who had SIRS prior to admission were already in evolving stage of sepsis. The difference in mortality between these two groups viz. one who had SIRS prior to admission(60%) and SIRS after admission(40%) was statically significant ($p=0.116$).

Bertrand Guidet et al^[2] studied the incidence and impact of organ dysfunction on sepsis in Paris in 2005. They observed that majority of patients with Severe Sepsis had two organ dysfunction. The three most frequent organ dysfunctions were respiratory, circulatory, and renal. Greg S Martin and Marc Moss^[10] studied the epidemiology of sepsis in United States in 2003. The organs that failed most frequently in patients with sepsis were the lungs (in 18 percent of patients) and the kidneys (in 15 percent of patients); less frequent were cardiovascular failure (7 percent), hematologic failure (6 percent), metabolic failure (4 percent), and neurologic failure (2 percent).

In our study, the most common organ involved in MODS was lung on day of admission and metabolic acidosis was the least amongst the feature of MODS. But involvement of lung and metabolic failure on day of admission had more unfavorable outcome (more mortality) compared to involvement of other organs.

On day of admission, the involvement of lung and metabolic failure seemed to have effect on outcome. This could be attributed to the fact that hypoxemia had detrimental effect on all organs of the body especially brain and heart. Metabolic acidosis had multiple etiologies. So presence of metabolic acidosis on day of admission would suggest there was gross derangement

in various parameters like hypoxia, hypoglycemia, hypotension, muscle fatigue and others. This is why metabolic acidosis was fatal as far as outcome was concerned.

However, after day 3, persistence of any organ failure had effect on prognosis. But involvement of hematologic parameter viz. platelet count did not affect outcome. This implies that if there are no signs of any organ improvement after 3 days it would indicate that chance of survival of such patients would be decreasing except for platelet count as it usually takes some time to improve (even though patient is recovering from sepsis).

Another interesting fact that emerged is that out of 24 patients who expired in whole study, 23 of them had involvement of lung. So the prognosis of patients who has involvement of lung in form of acute lung injury or ARDS during patient's illness is always guarded. We had ventilated this patients using standard ventilatory care. Patients with ARDs were followed on standard protocol of low tidal volume, optimum PEEP (according to blood pressure), and were sedated with midazolam and fentanyl (dose and requirement varied in each individual).

It is very important to know the effect of various costly advanced modalities of treatment for sepsis. As we have seen aggressive modes of therapy like ventilator, vasopressor, dialysis and surgical intervention didn't seem to have altered the prognosis. This thereby indicates that difference in survival group and non-survival group for use of all above-mentioned therapy was statistically not significant. This could also mean that once the organ failure sets in, even the most aggressive therapy of organ support might not prove fruitful.

The average length of total stay in survival group was around 15 days, with majority of these patients being in ICU. The patients who expired were in ICU only during their entire hospital stay. This would be important for ICU administrator as well as hospital administrator to plan out the cost-effective services and to know the cost implications. Hence it seems sepsis is synonymous with ICU as mentioned by Paul Marik and Joseph in 1997.^[11]

CONCLUSION:

The difference of mortality between MODS and severe sepsis group for mortality was statistically significant. Patients who had lung and metabolic acidosis on day of admission had unfavorable outcome.

The persistence of any organ failures (except hematological) after 3rd days had increased mortality. Prognosis of the patients will be better if they report before the development of MODS.

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